

Efficient Collaboration in Interdisciplinary Teams – an Electromobility Research Example

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1. Introduction

Researchers from the [ZDIN-ZLE](#) (“Zentrum für digitale Innovationen Niedersachsen, Zukunftslabor Energie”, English: Center for Digital Innovations, Future Laboratory Energy) project documented their methodologies and created a best practice for an efficient and effective research process in interdisciplinary teams using their experience of investigating the grid integration of electric vehicles in existing residential districts. This research has been one of several research directions within the project. The research focused on energy system modeling and was based on open science standards to ensure knowledge transfer, transparency, and re-usability of the developed (co-)simulation models and scenarios. The presented best practice respectively its methodological approach is divided into five successive phases, in which continuous cooperation took place and publication opportunities were used at an early stage. Figure 1 provides an overview of the chosen research process.

Figure 1. Overview of the research process.

The research process is described successively in the following sections according to the sub-processes and phases illustrated in Figure 1.

2. Continuous collaboration and early identification of publication opportunities

Collaboration within the team was systematically organized and planned. Appointing one person to lead the research process ensured efficiency. A precise target date defined from the beginning facilitated milestone planning. Interim results were presented and the following steps were discussed in two-weekly jour-fixes. The jour-fixes were documented to track progress. An agile project management tool, including options for milestone planning and visualization of Gantt charts, was used for project tracking and time scheduling. Informal digital communication channels, i.e. messenger applications, enabled participants to exchange ideas at any time, discuss interim results, collect feedback at short notice, and organize virtual meetings. This promoted the identification and preparation for early publication opportunities.

Thus, a transfer to scientific literature was ensured at three points in the research process. In the first publication, a systematic literature review was conducted using research methods from the energy and information systems domains to identify research gaps, research needs, and requirements [1]. Moreover, a research agenda was derived from the literature reviews' results guiding the further research. In the second publication, the developed modeling approach and the associated tool selection were presented to a broad specialist audience in the field of computer science with a distinctive talk format [2]. In the third publication, a special technological capability, i.e., the developed control mechanism for grid integration of the electric vehicles, was verified in a separate publication in order to obtain the necessary level of detail [3]. In the fourth publication, the developed tool for analyzing district energy systems was published for the scientific community along with an illustrative case study [4]. This included publishing the developed models, scenarios, and used data [5]. All articles are published in peer-reviewed outlets. In addition, the focus was placed on conference contributions to encourage direct discussions with other scientists and further promote interdisciplinary exchange.

3. Competence identification

The first step was to conduct a competence analysis of the interdisciplinary team to optimize the use of the participants' individual strengths and knowledge base. Thereafter, based on the initial research proposal, work packages as part of the overarching research process that required investigation in the context of the digitization of energy systems were identified. The project team members then assigned themselves to the work packages based on their competence and interests. The self-assignment ensured a high level of intrinsic motivation. In addition to the members' individual competence, the competence of the participating institutes was also considered. Moreover, the project teams' competence was further enhanced through selective training, e.g., on software quality, over the course of the collaboration.

4. Literature review, research needs and research questions

The underlying research example of electric vehicle integration in districts showed many publications, with over 80 apposite papers in the last ten years. Therefore, a text-mining-based tool was used to encompass relevant literature and identify trends. From this, it was possible to deduce that the majority of the papers declared similar tasks as further research. At the same time, it was revealed that the topics often overlap or have been examined several times. It was concluded that open source software could be a solution, as it allows to avoid duplicated research and enhances the re-usability of artifacts. Thereafter, inspired by the preliminary work of one of the participating research institutes [6] and refined by the results of the literature review, research questions were formulated and addressed in the ongoing research process that addressed the goal of implementing an open source tool for analyzing the grid capacity of districts for electric vehicles.

5. Modeling

Knowledge of programming languages and tools for energy system analysis was included in identifying the skills to enable joint work on the modeling phase. Further criteria for selecting the simulation framework and models included modularization and re-usability. In particular, the focus was on the transparency and verifiability of the research results to be obtained. Data and models were viewed and selected from open access databases from the energy domain. If self-developed models were required, attention was paid to ensure re-usability in the community. Hence, the co-simulation framework mosaik was chosen [7], and all self-created models were developed accordingly.

6. Case study

For validation and demonstration purposes, a case study was conducted by modeling of a project-relevant district. Specifically, the “Am Ölper Berge” district in Braunschweig, Lower Saxony, Germany, was selected and its grid capacity for electric vehicles was analyzed [4]. The needs of the district were analyzed in detail and corresponding scenarios were developed. This included case-related data collection. Resulting simulation scenarios enabled sensitivity analyzes for increasing the grid capacity for electric vehicles through user-oriented improvement measures that map components for cooperative energy generation and storage with the necessary central control systems.

7. Knowledge transfer and open science

The scientists at ZDIN-ZLE committed themselves to an open science approach in their “Open Science Declaration” from the very beginning of the project, including the presented research process [8]. All developed scenarios and models are freely available in a public repository [5]. The data collected and created for the case study is also available in the public repository [5]. The chosen open science approach ensures transparency and enables an easy and highly accessible knowledge transfer and fast and continuous development within energy system modeling. The method described was additionally presented and discussed as a poster at the 6th Applied Economics Workshop 2024 in Hanover [9].

Data availability statement

The source code and associated documentation are available at [5]. The basis of this abstract is the version with the tag “Deliverable_D1.3_Zukunftslabor_Energie_ZN3488”.

Authors' contributions

Henrik Wagner: Writing – original draft, Software. **Sarah Eckhoff:** Writing – original draft. **Sarah Lier:** Writing – original draft. **Sarah Fayed:** Writing – review & editing, Software. **Fernando Penaherrera V.:** Writing – review & editing, Software. **Michael H. Breitner:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Bernd Engel:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Sebastian Lehnhoff:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Johannes Rolink:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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References

1. S. Eckhoff, H. Wagner, O. Werth, J. Gerlach, M. H. Breitner, B. Engel, “Electric mobility integration in energy communities: trending topics and future research directions,” presented at the 5th E-Mobility Power System Integration Symposium (EMOB 2021), Hybrid Conference, Germany, Sep. 2021: IET, pp. 196–204. doi: 10.1049/icp.2021.2524
2. H. Wagner, S. Eckhoff, S. Fayed, F. Peñaherrera V., A. Ofenloch, O. Werth, B. Engel, M. Breitner, S. Lehnhoff, J. Rolink: Analysis of the Grid Capacity for Electric Vehicles in Districts with a Major Need for Sustainable Energy Refurbishment: The Case of a District in Lower Saxony, *Environmental Informatics – A bogeyman or saviour to achieve the UN Sustainable Development Goals? - Adjunct Proceedings of the 35th EnviroInfo Conference, EnviroInfo, Berlin, Berlin: Shaker, 27.-29. September 2021, S. 65-66. ISBN 978-3-8440-8329-3. doi: 10.2370/9783844083293*
3. S. Fayed, F. Penaherrera Vaca, H. Wagner, J. Rolink, “An Open Source Grid Observer for the Analysis of Power Flexibilities in Low Voltage Distribution Grid Simulations,” presented at the 10th International Conference on Smart Grid and Clean Energy Technologies, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Oct. 2022. doi: 10.1109/ICSGCE55997.2022.9953716
4. H. Wagner, F. Penaherrera Vaca, S. Fayed, O. Werth, S. Eckhoff, B. Engel, et al., “Co-Simulation-Based Analysis of the Grid Capacity for Electric Vehicles in Districts: The Case of “Am Ölper Berge” in Lower Saxony,” presented at the 6th E-Mobility Power System Integration Symposium, Den Haag, Netherlands, Oct. 2022. doi: 10.1049/icp.2022.2713
5. H. Wagner, F. Penaherrera Vaca, S. Fayed, “Grid Capacity for Electric Mobility in Existing Districts,” 2022, Gitlab-Repository 2022. Available at <https://gitlab.com/zdin-zle/scenarios/grid-capacity-for-electric-mobility>, checked on 11/6/2024.
6. H. Wagner, J. Wussow, B. Engel, “NOVA Measures in Suburban Low Voltage Grids with an Inhomogeneous Distribution of Electric Vehicles,” presented at the 4th E-Mobility Power System Integration Symposium, Darmstadt, Germany: Energynautics GmbH, Nov. 2022. ISBN 978-3-9820080-6-6. Available at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346039201_NOVA_Measures_in_Suburban_Low_Voltage_Grids_with_an_Inhomogeneous_Distribution_of_Electric_Vehicles, checked on 11/6/2024.
7. A. Ofenloch et al., “MOSAİK 3.0: Combining Time-Stepped and Discrete Event Simulation,” 2022 Open Source Modelling and Simulation of Energy Systems (OSMSES), Aachen, Germany, 2022, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/OSMSES54027.2022.9769116
8. S. Ferez, F. Penaherrera Vaca, H. Wagner, S. Eckhoff, S. Fayed, T. Lege, et al., “ZLE Open Science Declaration,” 2021, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5221234
9. H. Wagner, S. Lier, S. Eckhoff, S. Fayed, F. Peñaherrera V., O. Werth, B. Engel, M. Breitner, S. Lehnhoff, J. Rolin, 6th Workshop of Applied Science, Hannover, Germany, 02.05-03.05.2024. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11567933